

MENTAL HEALTH STABILITY AND STRESS MANAGEMENT OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. The mental health stability and stress management of teachers have become increasingly critical topics in the field of education. The respondents of this study were composed of 120 teachers within Maa District, Division of Davao City. The researcher sets the criteria inclusion of respondents. The respondents must be public elementary school teachers, from Maa District, Division of Davao City. This abstract provides a concise overview of the issues, emphasizing their importance and the key strategies for addressing them. Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the future by educating the next generation, yet they often experience high levels of stress due to various professional challenges. Prolonged exposure to stress can have severe consequences on their mental health, potentially leading to burnout, anxiety, and depression. These adverse effects not only impact teachers personally but also influence their ability to provide effective education to students.

KEY WORDS

1. Mental Health Stability.
2. Stress Management.
3. Effective Education.

1. Introduction

The Problem and Its Setting According to Ledesma (2022), the ability to feel in control of one's thoughts and actions is a sign of mental health stability. Education-related difficulties put teachers under stress and jeopardize their health, which impairs their ability to teach. The impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak on humanity is unmatched. Millions of people died because of the pandemic's extraordinary disaster, which spread like wildfire and affected the entire world. This has led to the closure of educational institutions, which may lead to questions about mental health stability knowing that self-efficacy, peer relationships, physical health status, and stress management of teachers during the implementation of full-blast face-to-face classes, considering cognitive-behavioral interventions, support systems, and personal strategies. As mental health stability and stress are psycho-social risk factors in every sector, the main aim of this research is to know the extent of Mental Health Stability and stress management of teachers during the implementation of full-blast face-to-face classes. Overseeing one's own thoughts and deeds is a sign of mental health stability. Challenges in the classroom cause learners to feel stressed out and put their health in danger, which impairs their ability to study (Ledesma, 2022). In the global context, the influence of the COVID-19 coronavirus on humanity is unmatched. It was stated by Carreon et al. (2021) that millions of people around the world lost their lives because of the pandemic's incredible disaster, which spread like wildfire. This nationwide closure will have an impact on more than 90

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—The research design of this study utilized a quantitative, descriptive-correlational method because this study determines the mental health stability and stress management of teachers during the full blast face-to-face classes. To illustrate this research design, Creswell (2015) stated that, it is a design that is used by investigators to describe and measure the degree of relationship between two variables or a set of scores. The researcher believe that a descriptive-correlational methods effective for this study, the researcher may be able to determine the relationship between the mental health stability and stress management of teachers during the full blast face-to-face classes, it is the most accurate design that can be used in accordance with the topic.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of this study were composed of 120 teachers within Maa District, Division of Davao City. The researcher sets the criteria inclusion of respondents. The respondents must be a public elementary school teacher, from Maa District, Division of Davao City. Lastly, the teachers' respondents agreed to answer the survey tool administered by the researcher. The research respondents honestly filled up the information needed in the structured survey questionnaire that will be distributed accordingly by the researcher. The researcher used a random sampling method in conducting the study, use a proportional number of respondents in every public elementary school belong to, public elementary school of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Simple random sampling was used, everyone was chosen and entirely by draw lots. Due to the large number of the population of teachers

in public elementary school at Maa District, Division of Davao City, such that everyone has the probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—A researcher self-made instrument was prepared with the guidance of the thesis adviser and evaluators and was used in gathering the needed data for the realization of the work. The questionnaire has 3 aspects (indicators) for the independent variable (mental health stability), self-efficacy, peer relationship and physical health status, while the dependent variable (stress management) considered the 3 indicators namely: cognitive behavioral interventions, support system, and personal strategies. Each indicator has five (5) questions that can be answered through the given legend. Simple instructions can be seen in the questionnaires. The research questionnaires where purely researcher made the concept of the questionnaire was submitted and was evaluated by a grammarian and validators. The suggestions and evaluation tools were given for them to help the researchers to improve and make the research instrument in its best form. The outcome of the evaluation and validation as well as the research instrument's draft was submitted to the research adviser for finalization. Unclear statements were removed; weak statements were strengthened and polished. After the finalization by the research adviser, the research instrument is now prepared. After the evaluation and approval of the questionnaires, the tool for gathering data and information from the respondents will be administered by the researcher. The pilot testing was conducted at the same area but not with the respondents of the study.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Extent of Mental Health Stability

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20–5:00	Very Extensive	Mental health stability is always evident.
3:40–4.19	Extensive	Mental health stability is oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Mental health stability is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Mental health stability is rarely evident.
1:00–1.79	Not Extensive	Mental health stability is never evident.

Extent of Stress Management

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20–5:00	Very Extensive	Stress management is always evident.
3:40–4.19	Extensive	Stress management is oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Stress management is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Stress management is rarely evident.
1:00–1.79	Not Extensive	Stress management is never evident.

The necessary data underwent the following gathering procedure: The researcher asked for an endorsement to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School. A letter request attached with the Dean’s endorsement was forwarded to the School’s Division Superintendent for permission. The researcher asks permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Davao City to conduct a survey to the 120 teachers respondents from Maa district, division of Davao City. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the principals and supervisor of public elementary schools, Maa district, Division of Davao City for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. The arrangement was done with the school principals and supervisor upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Upon the approval, the researcher personally administered the research survey tool. The researcher conducted the survey and retrieved the data. The researcher observed full ethical standards in the conduct of the study, following the study protocol assess-

ment and standardized criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. A received copy of the letter presented was secured from the principals to vouch that the researcher honestly conducted and collected the data from the respondents of the study. The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially and accordingly. The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study. After the responses may be retrieved and tallied, and then be forwarded to the statistician for data treatment. The 120 teachers’ respondents from Maa District, Division of Davao City have given their free will to participate or to withdraw anytime from the study without any form of consequence or penalty. The respondents personally and professionally give an information that may be required in the study was kept in private and were treated with utmost confidentiality of the respondents’ data was adhered upon. On the other hand, the research questionnaire used is free of technical terms and can be easily understood by the respondents of the study, these perceived biases are prevented. Therefore, no research

questionnaire was given to respondents without the permission from the authorized command channels.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools may be used to treat the data: Mean. This may be to determine the extent of the mental health stability and stress management of teachers. Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. This tool may be used to determine the relationship between the mental health stability and stress management of teachers. Regression. This tool may be used to determine the domain of the mental health stability significantly influence of stress management of teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted. Summary of the extent of Mental Health Presented in Table 4 are data on the summary of the extent of mental health. The overall mean of the data is 3.99 which distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: Self-efficacy 3.96, Peer Relationship 4.00, and Physical Health Status 4.01. All these indicators are with the descriptive equivalent of extensive which means that the indicators that may considered of this study in mental health.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Mental Health Indicators

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Self-efficacy	3.96	Extensive
Poor visual attention	4.00	Extensive
Physical Health Status	4.01	Extensive
Overall mean	3.99	Extensive

Further discussion by Li et al (2021). conducted a systematic review of studies on the relationship between teacher burnout and physical health. The review found that higher levels of burnout were associated with poorer physical health outcomes among teachers, including higher levels of chronic conditions, physical symptoms, and absenteeism. Supported by Liu et al. (2021) conducted a meta-analysis of studies on the relationship between teacher stress and health outcomes. The analysis found that higher levels of stress were associated with poorer physical and mental health outcomes among teachers, including higher levels of chronic conditions, physical symptoms, and mental health issues such as depression and

anxiety. These studies suggest that teachers’ physical health status plays an important role in their mental health stability. Poor physical health, including chronic conditions and physical symptoms, can contribute to higher levels of stress, burnout, and mental health issues among teachers. The studies highlight the importance of promoting and supporting teachers’ physical health as a key component of promoting their mental health and well-being. Mental health is perceived as a positive source contributing to asset development individually, socially, and economically (WHO, 2020). Stress Management

The authors discuss the In that matter, there should be sufficient PPE availability and de-

tailed rules about its use, limited hours in each shift, dissemination of medical information through multiple platforms and languages, education about skills to deal with the patients psychological concerns, delaying of elective appointments and surgeries and, if possible, assembly of a backup force composed of capable retired workers and college students about to graduate for the times of higher patient volume (Dutheil et al., 2020; Santarone et al., 2020; Zaka et al., 2020). The role of positive emotions in positive psychology: The broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions. American psychologist (Fredrickson, B. L. (2021). This study by Fredrickson proposes the broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions, which suggests

that positive emotions broaden an individual’s thought-action repertoire, which in turn leads to increased well-being and resilience. The author discusses the ways in which positive emotions contribute to social-emotional well-being Masten, A. S., Reed, M. G. (2020). Summary of Stress Management

The table below shows the summary of stress management. It plays a crucial role in their stress management, stress management can be influenced by cognitive behavioral interventions, support system, and personal strategies. These cognitive processes impact students’ reading fluency, comprehension, and overall stress management.

Table 2. Summary of Stress Management Indicators

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Cognitive Behavioral Interventions	4.02	Extensive
Support System	3.99	Extensive
Personal Strategies	4.05	Extensive
Overall mean	4.01	Extensive

Table 8 shows a summary of summary of stress management which revealed an overall mean of 4.01. The four indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating namely cognitive behavioral interventions 4.02, support system 3.99, and personal strategies 4.05. All three indicators are with the descriptive equivalent of extensive. Which means that summary of stress management goals is to plan for the replacement of key strategies; potential teachers must first be identified and prepared to take on those roles, it is not enough to select teachers in the school who seem "right" for the job. Not only should the experience and duties be considered, but stress management also which revealed cognitive behavioral, support system and personal strategies has descriptive equivalent of extensive. Working memory, interventions,

including problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, social support, physical exercise, CBT, and mindfulness-based interventions, can be effective in reducing stress levels and promoting mental health and well-being among teachers. The studies highlight the importance of providing teachers with a range of resources and support for managing stress and building resilience.

Significant relationship between the mental health and stress management

The significant relationship between the mental health and stress management has a strong relationship in a work is necessary to be united and to have work collaboration which can be gain by having both positive teaching strategies and a strong working relationship.

Table 3. Correlation between Mental Health and Stress Management

Variables	Mean	Std	R	Sig. Level ($\alpha < .05$)
Mental Health	4.00	.400	.412	.000
Stress Management	4.01	.401		

Note. H_0 : Null Hypothesis

Table 9 had shown the significant relationship between the mental health and stress management got mean rating of 4.00 with the standard deviation of 0.400 and difficulties stress management got the mean rating of 4.01 with the standard deviation of 0.401 standard deviation. The Pearson-R correlation result showed 0.412 which means there is a positive correlation at a significant level of .000 which means that there is a significant relationship between the mental health and stress management. It explains that if mental health and stress management. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significant relationship between of mental health and stress management, the result of the study implied the that the indicators of mental health significantly influence to the and stress management. Hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. However, as evidence from the literature review, many studies have been done stress management of elementary school teachers plays a crucial role in their mental health. Mental health can be influenced by various stress management factors, including mental health stability in terms of self-efficacy, peer relationship, physical health status and stress management in terms cognitive behavioral interventions, support system, personal strategies. By addressing and supporting teachers with mental health, we can directly contribute to their mental health and overall stress management. By providing targeted interventions, implementing evidence-based strategies, and fostering a supportive learning envi-

ronment, we empower teachers to overcome mental health, strengthen their stress management, and unlock their full potential as confident and proficient readers. As complex and multi-component activities, arts and crafts have been highly associated with a diminished risk of developing mental health disorders (Conejero et al., 2020). It is suspected that they modulate several neurotransmitters, as well as cortisol levels, and stimulate neuroplasticity (Conejero et al., 2020). Therefore, they offer the possibility of emotional expression and regulation. Moreover, an adequate work environment is essential to diminish the mental health impact of the pandemic on healthcare professionals. They include seeking and reaching out to social connections, such as friends or family, or even volunteering, as reducing the feeling of loneliness and enhancing belongingness is crucial to preventing suicide (Holmes et al., 2020). Keeping oneself committed to other things (i.e., hobbies, music, reading, film, television, and home improvements) and engaging in enjoyable activities to improve one’s mood have also been suggested (Restubog et al., 2020). The domain of mental health Significantly Influence the stress management

The domain of mental health significantly influences the stress management. Mental Health, such as poor phonological awareness, limited working memory capacity, or challenges in visual attention, can hinder students’ ability to effectively engage with and understand text. This mental health their stress management, inhibiting the development of critical

skills like comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and critical thinking.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of Mental Health Domains on Stress Management

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	F	p-value	Decision on H_0
Self-efficacy	Stress Management	4.106	0.001	Reject H_0
Peer Relationship	Stress Management	4.112	0.005	Reject H_0
Physical Health Status	Stress Management	5.106	0.001	Reject H_0
Model				
Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Decision				
Regression	5.660	2.830	26.43	.000
Residual	6.960			
Total	12.619			

Note. H_0 = Null Hypothesis

Table 10 has shown that mental health significantly influences to the stress management it shows that the value of the regression analysis F ratio is 26.43, with a significant level of .000. This simply means that the mental health indicators significantly influence stress management. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This implied that there is a domain of mental health which refers to the ability to temporarily hold and manipulate information in the mind. It plays a crucial role in mental health, as teachers often deal with responsibilities. This can lead to high levels of stress and burnout, which can negatively impact their mental health. Ability to retain and organize information, leading to challenges in understanding and recalling what was read. Phonological awareness involves the ability to recognize and manipulate the sounds of spoken language. It is a mental health, as it enables to decode words and understand the relationships between sounds and

letters. Prolonged exposure to high levels of stress can lead to mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and even physical health problems. Teachers may experience symptoms like fatigue, irritability, and emotional exhaustion. Effective stress management is crucial for teachers to maintain their mental health. This can involve strategies such as time management, setting boundaries, seeking support, and practicing self-care. Achieving a work-life balance is essential for reducing stress. Teachers who can effectively separate their work from their personal life are better equipped to manage the demands of their profession and maintain their mental health stability. Having a strong support system, including colleagues, administrators, and access to mental health resources, can make a significant difference in a teacher's ability to manage stress and maintain mental health. The overall school culture plays a role in teacher mental health. Supportive, respectful, and inclu-

sive environments can reduce stress, whereas toxic or unsupportive cultures can exacerbate it. Challenging student behavior and disciplinary issues can add to a teacher's stress. Effective classroom management and behavior intervention strategies can help mitigate this stress.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the focal points of the research and the results of the statistical analysis. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings of the study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the relationship between mental health stability and stress management. The Pearson-R correlation result means there is a positive correlation at a significant level which means that there is a significant relationship between the mental health and stress management. It explains that if the mental health were positively embodied the stress management of teachers would be vertically significant and very extensive. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the mental health and stress management of teachers. The results of the study disclosed that the teacher firmly believes that the domain of mental health significantly influences stress management in teachers. Mental health can impact various stress management. Here is a statement that reflects this belief: The domain of mental health significantly influences stress management. These difficulties impact their cognitive processes, inhibiting the development of critical skills like comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and critical thinking. By addressing and supporting teachers with mental health, we can directly contribute to their stress management. By providing targeted interventions, implementing evidence-based strategies, and fostering a supportive learning environment, we empower teacher to overcome mental health, and stress management.

4.2. Conclusions—This research highlights a crucial issue that demands immediate attention. Stress and demanding work environments can adversely affect the mental health of

teachers, leading to conditions like anxiety and depression. This not only affects the individual teacher but also impacts their ability to effectively educate students. Therefore, it is vital to take preventative measures to promote mental health stability among teachers. They can take individual responsibility for their mental health by practicing self-care and building resilience. This may include setting boundaries, seeking social support, and engaging in stress-relieving activities like exercise or mindfulness. Let's join hands to create a supportive work environment that prioritizes the mental health of our teachers.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered for consideration: The officials of the Department of Education are considering making initiatives to develop further the in conclusion, the domain of mental health significantly influences stress management. Provide mandatory mental health awareness and training programs for teachers to help them identify and address mental health issues in themselves and their students. Encourage open conversations about mental health to reduce stigma and create a supportive culture within schools. Implement workload assessments to ensure that teachers' tasks are reasonable and manageable. Consider reducing administrative burdens and non-teaching responsibilities to allow teachers to focus on their primary role. Offer professional development opportunities related to stress management, self-care, and resilience-building. Provide training

on classroom management and behavior strategies to reduce the stress associated with discipline issues. Encourage school leadership to be empathetic and approachable, creating an environment where teachers feel comfortable discussing their concerns. Promote a healthy work-life balance by modeling it among school leaders. Ensure that mental health resources such as counseling services, Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs), and wellness initiatives are readily available to teachers. Establish clear pathways for teachers to seek help and support if they are experiencing mental health challenges. Encourage the formation of peer support networks or mentorship programs among teachers where they can share experiences and coping strategies. Foster a sense of community and mutual support within the teaching staff. Educate teachers on the importance of self-care and provide guidance on stress reduction techniques, such as mindfulness, exercise, and time management. Promote regular breaks and encourage teachers to use their vacation time to recharge. Acknowledge and reward teachers for their hard work and dedication, celebrating their successes and contributions. Recognize the additional efforts teachers have made, especially during challenging times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Lastly, the results and findings of this study will challenge future researchers to conduct a similar study that must consider other factors that could help the new education system in the Philippines quality and valuable in all aspects.

5. References

- Afe JO (2019). *Reflections on becoming a teacher and the challenges of teacher education. Inaugural Lecture Series 64*. Benin City: University of Benin, Nigeria. Uchefuna MC 2001. A Study of Clinical Supervision and Teachers Effectiveness in Umuahia and Abia Educational Zones of Abia State. M.Ed Dissertation, Unpublished, Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Anastasi D. (2018). *Parent-child relationship, home learning environment, and school readiness*. School Psychology Review.
- Anderson, A. (2017). *Source: Supplied*. We can set high expectations for the behavior of public-school students. The Sunday Telegraph. Retrieved las February 01, 2014 10: 00pm. <http://www.dailytelegraph.com.au/news/nsw/we-can-set-high-expectations-for-the-behaviour-of-public-school-students/story-fni0cx12-1226815665143>
- Anil c. (2018). Research in Australian university economic departments. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australian association for research in education. Armidale, NSW.
- Ballantyne, R. & Packer, J. (2016). Teaching and learning in environmental education: Developing environmental conceptions. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 27, 25-32.
- Banzon, R. (2019). *Emotional quotient and classroom management competence of Binugao National High teachers: Effects on Students performance*. Unpublished Masteral Thesis, University of Immaculate Conception, Davao City.
- Belot, M., & James, J. (2018). Healthy school meals and educational outcomes. *Journal of Health Economics*, 30, 489–504.
- Bendtro, Larry K., Broken leg, Martin, and Van Bockern, Steve (2018). *Reclaiming Youth at Risk: Our Hope for the Future*, Revised Edition. Bloomington IN: Solution Tree (formerly National Education Service).
- Berry, Michael A., (2019). *Protecting the Built Environment--Cleaning for Health*, TriComm 21st Press, Chapel Hill, NC, 2003.
- Berry, Michael A., "Assessing the Risks of Indoor Air", in *Indoor Air Quality in Homes: Synthesizing the Issues and Educating Consumers*, pp. 17-21, American Association of Housing Educators and Building Research Council-Small Homes Council, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 2001.
- Bersabe D (2017). *Child friendly Learning Environment and Learners Development*. Unpublished Masteral Thesis. University of Southeastern Phillipines. Davao City.

- Bessant F. (2019). Child friendly basic education and learning initiative in Canada: Casw study of selected UNICEF focus district.
- Bristol R. (2018). The European Commission,2010. A comprehensive framework for effective schoolimprovement in new perspective for learning.
- Bwonda, Eldah N., and Enos H. Njeru. Primary Education in Kenya: Access and Policy Implications, 1989-2002. Working paper no. 62. Nairobi: Institute of Policy Analysis and Research, 2005.
- Bluestein, Jane, Ph.D. (2018) Creating Emotionally Safe Schools: A Guide for Educators and Parents. Deerfield Beach, FL: Health Communications, Inc.
- Blum, Robert W. (2018). "School Connectedness: Improving the Lives of Students." Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health.
- Blum, Robert W., McNeely, Clea, and Rinehart, Peggy Mann (2018). "Improving the Odds: The Untapped Power of Schools to Improve the Health of Teens." Minneapolis, MN: Center for Adolescent Health and Development, University of Minnesota.
- Carter, L. (2019). parents on your side: A comprehensive parent involvement program for teacher. Lee Carter and Association, USA,.
- Chaika D. (2017). Ethical considerations in gender-oriented entertainment technology, crossroads association for computing machinery.
- Chan, Tak Cheung. (2019). Physical Environment and Middle Grade Achievement. Greenville, SC: Greenville County School District, 2000. ERIC ED 198 645.
- Creemers E. (2019).FAUSA adopts policy on the performance indicators. FAUSA Newa ^.
- Chabot, Lise, Engaging First Nations Parents in Education: An Examination of Best Practices. A Manifesto for Education in Ontario, Chiefs of Ontario, 2017.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Division of Adolescent and School Health (2019). Student health and academic achievement. http://www.cdc/HealthyYouth/health_and_academics/index.htm. Retrieved on February 19, 2009.
- Cerini, B, Murray, I and Reiss, M (2018) Student review of the science curriculum: major findings, NESTA, London, <http://www.planet-science.com/sciteach/review/Findings.pdf>

- Cuttance P. (2019). Performance indicators for schooling: A report for Scottish Education.
- Cook, J. (2018). The Importance of Learning ScienceeHowEducationK-12. The Importance of Learning Science more: http://www.ehow.com/about_6169591_importance-learning-science.html#ixzz2rfRYkVMh
- Damon, W. (2018). *The moral child: Nurturing children's natural moral growth*. New York: Free Press.
- David C. (2018). Closing the gender gap: gender gaps fact sheet. American association of university women.
- DeCos, P.L. (1997, December). *Readiness for kindergarten: What does it mean?* Sacramento, CA: California Research Bureau, California State Library. Summary available online: <http://www.library.ca.gov/html/statseg2a.cfm#CRB-97-14>. Full document also available online (requires Adobe Acrobat software): <http://www.library.ca.gov/CRB/97/14/97014.pdf>
- Demarest, E.J., Reisner, E.R., Anderson, L.M., Humphrey, D.C., Farquhar, E., & Stein, S.E. (2018). *Review of research on achieving the nation's readiness goal*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education.
- De Guzman Jr. and Guy I (2018). Teacher's Time Management and Student's Academic Achievement in LPU College of Nursing: Basis for an Enhanced Classroom Management Lyceum of the Philippines University Batangas City, Batangas Philippines
- Douglas K. (2016). Educators play key role in promoting gender equity. Horizon. Midwest desegregation assistance center.
- Dunnell P. & O'Loughlin MJ. (2017). A framework for the development of performance indicators in an education system. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australia.
- Edwards M. (2019). Social change and transformation of human relationship: McGraw Hill INC.
- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., et al. (2017). Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Estes, C. (2019). *Promoting Students Centered Learning in Experiential Education*. Journal of Experiential Education.

- Feng, N. (2019). *An examination of children's educational computing at home*. Cambridge University Press: Great Britain, 2010.
- Foster, A. (2018). *Decision criteria for assessing one-dimensionality: An empirical study*. Multivariate behavioral research.
- Freiberg, H. Jerome, (2018) *School Climate: Measuring, Improving and Sustaining Healthy Learning Environments*. Philadelphia, PA: Falmer Press, 2005.
- Gallagher-Hayashi, Diane (2019) *Connecting with Aboriginal Students*. *Teacher Librarian*; June; 31,5, pp. 20-24.
- Gagne, E.D., Yekovich, C. W., and Yekovich, F.R (2018). *The Cognitive Psychology of School Learning*.
- Genesee, F. (2019). *Integrating Language and Content: Lessons from Immersion*. Educational Practice Report.
- Good, B. (2018). *Measurement and Evaluation*. Retrieved February 24, 2010 from <http://www.livesearch.msn>
- Griffiths, R. F. (2019). *Time management in telework and other autonomous work environments*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Kansas State University.
- Grigg, L. & Sheehan, P. (2019). *Evaluating research: The role of performance indicators*. The University of Queensland.
- Hargreaves, D. (2019). *Education Epidemic – Transforming secondary schools through innovation networks*. London: Demos.
- Hawkins, A. (2018). *Gender and technological imagination*. Presented at the American Educational Research Association, Boston, MA. 2008.
- Herbilla L (2018). *Study habits and time management*. Katigaman Journal. Dep.Ed.
- Hilburion C (2019). *Extent of implementation of child-friendly school system: Basis for school performance indicators*. Unpublished material thesis. Rizal Memorial Colleges.
- Holzinger, O. (2019). *Technology Gender Gap Develops While Gaps in Math and Science Narrow, AAUW Foundation Report Shows*. American Association of University Women, 2009.
- Huang, X. & Zhan, Z. (2018). *The compiling of adolescence time management disposition inventory*. *Acta Psychological Sinic*, 33(4), 338-343.

- Izard, C., Kagan, J., & Zajonc, R. (2019). *Emotions, cognition, and behavior*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Iyoshi, R. (2019). *Cognitive Tools and Student-centered Learning: Rethinking Tools, Functions and Applications*. Educational Media International.
- Jamison, T. (2017). *Productivity ratios of graduate's programs in psychology based on publication in the journals of the American Psychological association*. American Psychologist.
- Kavanagh, Barbara. (2018). *The Role of Parental and Community Involvement in the Success of First Nations Learners: A Review of the Literature written for the Minister's National Working Group on the First Nations Education, Indian and Northern Affairs Canada*.
- Knudsen, M. (2019). *Education standards agency, Assessment of the impact of the environment on the quality basic education and gender parity in primary school*, National Evaluation Reports, Germany.
- Kristjansson, E., Robinson, V., Petticrew, M., MacDonald, B., Krasevec, J., Janzen, L., Greenhalgh, T., Wells, G., MacGowan, J., Farmer, A., Shea, B. J., Mayhew, A., and Tugwell, P., (2007). "School Feeding for Improving the Physical and Psychosocial Health of Disadvantaged Elementary School Children." Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews.
- Lahey, B. B. (2017). *Psychology: an introduction*. 8th ed. Boston: McGraw Hill.
- Levin, S. (2019). *A Comparison of Assessment Practices and Their Effects on Learning Motivation in a Student-centered Learning Environment*. Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia.
- Macintosh, F. (2017). *Teachers' Beliefs about Issues in the implementation of a Student-Centered Learning Environment*. Educational Technology, Research and Development.
- Malone, K. & Tranter, P. (2018) "Children Environmental learning and the Use, design and Management of school grounds." *Children, Youth and Environments* 13(2), 2003.
- Mapula (2019) challenges of k-12 program and managements skills of public elementary school principals in Davao city. Unpublished Masteral Thesis
- Martimore, S. (2019). *The Difference Made by Schools: School Effectiveness and School Improvement Studies*. LARTV Seminar Series. No. 1

- Marzano, R. J., Waters, T., & McNulty, B. A. (2018). *School leadership that works: From research to results*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Mason M (2017). Thoughts on Leadership: How Important is Decision-Making? <http://www.moyak.com/papers/leadership-qualities.html>.
- Mendes, K. (2018). *Educational reform in Uganda reflections on policy, partnership, strategy and implementation*, UK department for International Development, London. The Efficiency of Public Education in Uganda, World Bank, Washington, D.C., 208.
- Miers, E. (2019). *NSW Department of Education and Training (NSW DET). 2004 Values in NSW Public Schools – a Ministerial Statement*. Sydney: NSW.
- Mock, R. (2018). *The quality of education and accountability*. Invited conference of educational management. Woodend, Victoria.
- Moeller, O. (2015). *Office for Standards in Education (Ofsted), 2004. A new relationship with schools*. London, Department of Education and Skills (DfES).’
- Morgan, G. (2016). *The World Bank Group. 2006. Accountability Processes and Mechanisms in Effective Schools and Teachers*.
- Motschnig, E. (2016). *Student-Centered Teaching Meets New Media: Concept and Case Study*. Educational Technology & Society.
- Murphy, N. (2018). *Higher education research policy*. Commonwealth government, Canberra.
- Murray, D. (2019). *World learning, ‘child-friendly schools baseline report’, child friendly basic education and learning programme*, UNICEF New York, USA.
- Nenyod, B. (2019). School-based management: Thai was and methods. Report to ONEC and ADB as a part of, TA 3585 – THA.
- Norris, S and Phillips, L (2019) How literacy in its fundamental sense is central to scientific literacy. *Education*, 87(2), 224-240.
- Osborne, J, Duschl, R. and Fairbrother, B (2019) Breaking the Mould? Teaching Science for Public Understanding, School of Education, King’s College London.
- Patton, A. (2018). *Department of Education Tasmania. Strategic Planning Framework: Accountability, Monitoring and Reporting*.
- Pederson, G. (2018). *South Australian Curriculum Standards and Accountability*.

- Philips, D. A., & Carlisle, C. (2018). *A comparison of physical education teachers categorized as most and least effective*. *Journal of Teaching in Physical*
- Realino(2019). Emotional Quotient and Management competence of teacher. Unpublished Masteral Thesis. Holy Cross of Davao College.
- Realino R. (2019). Emotional intelligence and Level of classroom management competence of teachers. Unpublished Masterless. University of Holy Cross of Davao College.
- Reid, K. (2017). *Diagnostic Study on Causes of Low Primary Education Completion Rates*, London, Ministry of Education and Sports.
- Reynolds, U. (2018) *School effectiveness research: A review of the international literature*. In D. Reynolds et al. (Eds.), *Advances in school effectiveness research and practice*. U.k.: Pergamon Press. 25-54.
- Roeser, R., Eccles, J., & Sameroff, A. (2018). School as a context of early adolescents' social-emotional development: A summary of research findings. *The Elementary School Journal*, 100(5), pp.443-471.
- Sakamoto, I. (2018). *Video game use and the development of socio-cognitive abilities in children: Three Surveys of elementary school students*. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 24, 2008.
- Schaffer, N. (2018). *Key Characteristics of Effective Schools: A review of school effectiveness research*. Institute of Education, University of London, for the Office for Standards in education. London: Institute of Education.
- Schaeffer, L. (2019). *United States of America. 2001. No Child Left Behind Act of 2001* (United States Legislation).
- Schultz, P., Gouveia, V., Cameron, L., Tankha, G., Schmuck, P. & Franek, M. (2018). *Values and their relationship to environmental concern and conservation behavior*. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 36, 457-475.
- Schreiner, C. & Sjøberg, S. (2018). *Sowing the seeds of ROSE. Background, Rationale, Questionnaire Development and Data Collection for ROSE (The Relevance of Science Education) - a comparative study of students' views of science and science education, Acta Didactica - (4/2004) (ISBN 82-90904-79-7), University of Oslo, Dept. of Teacher Education and School*
- Sevilla C. Ochava J., Punsalan W., Regala, & Uriate G. (2018). *Research method*. Revised edition. Rex Bookstore. Quezon City. Philippines

- Sheerens, I. (2018). *Improving School Effectiveness*. Fundamentals of Education Planning. Series, No. 68. International Institute for Educational Planning. UNESCO. Paris No 69. (See Charts 7 and 88, p 45 – 48) For a copy, please email: information@iiep.unesco.org.
- Short, D. (2019) Assessing Integrated Language and Content Instruction. *TESOL Quarterly*, 27, 4.
- Snodgrass, N. (2018). *Why not try some new ways of measuring quality?* *Educational Record*, 63.
- Society of State Directors of Health, Physical Education and Recreation & Association of State and Territorial Health Officials. (2002) *Making the Connection: Health and Student Achievement*. <http://thesociety.org/pdf/makingtheconnection.ppt>. Retrieved February 19, 2009.
- Stoner, Freeman and Gilbert, (2018). *Management*. Prentice. Hall, 6th ed. printed. Catalogue Description
- Tan, A. (2017). *Mass Communication theories in the classroom settings*: Mc Millan Publishing Co.
- Taylor, M., Coovadia, H. M., Kvalsvig, J. D., Jinabhai, C. C. and Reddy, P. (2018) Helminth control as an entry point for health-promoting schools in KwaZulu-Natal. *South African Medical Journal*, 89, 273–279.
- Taylor, B. (2018). Teaching ESL: Incorporating a Communicative, student-centered component. *TESOL Quarterly*, 17, 1, 69-88.
- Topel, G. (2018). *Learning perform situation in the pilot schools: Lesson and policy recommendations*. Report to ONEC and ADB as part of TA 3585-THA.
- UNESCO (2020). *FRESH: A Comprehensive School Health Approach to Achieve EFA*. Paris. (ED-2002/WS/8 Rev.).
- UNESCO (2018). *Embracing diversity. Toolkit for learning environments*. Bangkok
- Victoria, K. (2019). *School Standards and Accountability*.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: HarvardUniversity Press.
- Wang, J. (2019). *Computer Toys R Us vs. Them*. Computer Confidence for Women, 2009.

Wessler, Stephen L. with contributing author Preble, William (2018). *The Respectful School: How Educators and Students Can Conquer Hate and Harassment*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

WHO (World Health Organization) (2018). Skills for health, skills-based health Education including life skills: an important component of a child-friendly/health-promoting school. Information Series on School Health, Document 9. WHO, Geneva? Available at www.who.int/school_youth_health/resources/en/.

Williams, V. (2017). *School effectiveness research: Dead end, damp squib or smouldering fuse issues in Educational Research*, 61(1), 2005.

Wishart, L. (2019). *Addressing child protection and group care issues*. Northwest Institute for Children and Families, University of Washington School of Social Work, Washington State.

Wong Wai Yi, Wavy (2016). *The Relationship between Time Management, Perceived Stress, Sleep Quality and Academic Performance among University Students*. Unpublished Bachelor thesis. Hongkong

Zhu Yuan (2018). Student –teacher bonds in the modern era. Updated :2008-01-12:19 at <http://www.chinadaily.com.cn>

www.vcn.bc.ca. -[http:// www.monbu.go.jp](http://www.monbu.go.jp). -[http:// www.Globalization101.org](http://www.Globalization101.org). -
[http:// www.theolocal.fr](http://www.theolocal.fr). -[http:// www.the Canadian encyclopedia.com](http://www.the Canadian encyclopedia.com). -[http:// www.ipsnews.net](http://www.ipsnews.net). -[http:// www.xinhuanet.com](http://www.xinhuanet.com). -[http:// www.infoplease.com](http://www.infoplease.com). -
[http:// www.pch.gc.ca](http://www.pch.gc.ca).